

Growth Hack Service Framework for Boleh Dicoba Digital Company Based on Growth Hacking Framework and Value Co-Creation Framework

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ABSTRACT: BDD growth hack service practice is close to Bohnsack and Liesner (2019) and Kohtamäki & Rajala (2016) growth hack framework but lacking in data analysis and testing. The author suggested a new framework that combines the growth hack framework and the value co-creation framework. New operational instructions include value creation agreements and A/B testing based on comparative analysis. BDD should also remind clients about value creation and discuss value in exchange and value in use assignments. The new framework should increase service quality and resource availability of BDD growth hack service.

KEYWORDS: Framework, Growth hack, Resource availability, Service, Service quality, Value creation.

INTRODUCTION

Growth Hacking focuses intensely on acquiring customers, retaining them, engaging them, and making them return repeatedly. It blends product development, analytics, and online marketing to generate, prioritize and test ideas for growth. A growth team should bring together staff who have a deep understanding of the strategy and business goals [1].

Digital Growth-Hack Consultation could boost digital performance if clients have low digital performance. Boleh Dicoba Digital (BDD) startup will design and develop a program for clients' businesses, aiming to multiply digital marketing impact. This service also offers a growth-hack manual with all the formats you need to accelerate your digital growth strategy.

The main business issue is to deliver this service as a quality service using a reliable framework and gain more clients using Growth Hack services. After all, BDD is a startup, they are moving fast, flexible, agile, and competitive. BDD has the best practice and many potentials to succeed in this service. A reliable framework would help them to hone their potential in track and direct them in handling various clients.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Growth hack service in digital marketing startups is growing as a phenomenon. Aside from growth hack, value co-creation is a theory about the practice of jointly developing new value—both materially and symbolically—in a contemporaneous, collaborative, peer-like manner. The distinctions between co-creation and co-production and the need to make them are still being discussed in the literature [2]. Value co-creation is being reviewed to complement the growth hack service BDD framework aspires.

A. Growth Hacking

Growth hack services and growth-hack agencies are later developed in Silicon Valley and top digital marketing firms globally. Yet these are considered new, there are no general answers or rules about how this service or agencies compose their products, how they are working with clients, how they are educating clients about growth hacks, or how much their involvement is for clients. After all, based on the growth hack taxonomy, growth hack brings together various best practices, concentrates them in a standardized way, and classifies them into actionable groups. The groups follow the customer lifecycle, enabling firms to choose a growth hacking pattern that fits their specific need [3]. Therefore, growth hack services and growth-hack agencies fit the taxonomy but compose their products differently as elaborated in some cases.

Figure I. Growth Hacking Framework [3]

The lean startup technique, often known as the lean philosophy, is followed by Bohnsack and Liesner's [3] Growth Hacking Framework, which is motivated by digital transformation. Growth hacking is represented in this graphic as the fusion of digital marketing strategies, data analysis, testing, coding, and automation.

B. Collaboration in B2B System for Value Creation

The co-creation of value is a major literary theme in the networked economy, with the B2B environment seeing an increase in the use of collaborative creation of new service offerings and co-production of value propositions. Value co-creation and the coproduction of value propositions are essential for understanding the inter-organizational, dynamic, and systems-oriented approach to value creation [4]. Interactions between actors within business ecosystems that are mutually advantageous are the basis for value co-creation, which can have an impact on ecosystem-level activities that affect innovation, strategy development, and competitiveness [4].

Figure II. Value Co-Creation Framework [4]

Service science is an emerging interdisciplinary field of inquiry that focuses on fundamental science, models, theories, and applications to promote service innovation, competition, and well-being through the co-creation of value. Practices of co-creation incorporate difficult-to-explain and convey tacit knowledge and abilities into dispositions that direct collaborative work [5]. In

service firms, co-creation is inherent since market offerings are genuinely formed during the service interaction [6]. The co-creation debate serves as the foundation for recent advances in service theory [7].

C. Conceptual Framework

BDD provides a growth hack service to establish service quality and add up resource availability by cutting unnecessary resource spending. Co-creation of value theory could support this service.

Figure III. Conceptual Framework

The current growth hack service BDD provides is qualified but lacks cooperativeness from clients. If BDD could establish co-creation of value with clients' representatives along with current qualified growth hacking competencies, it could cut unnecessary resources spending and increase service quality. The concepts of value co-creation and the coproduction of value propositions enable comprehension of the inter-organizational, dynamic, and systems-oriented approach to value creation [4]. Co-creation theory would be an added value for the framework since the service requires clients' representative collaboration. The research output is a growth hack framework for BDD's service.

RESEARCH METHOD

This research used comparative case studies that also belong to the term multiple case studies umbrella, since the multiple-case study generates more convincing evidence, making the study stronger than the single-case study. Whereas comparative case studies are fitting due to this research's objectives needing to fix the current situation based on better references. To compose a multiple-case study, researchers must summarize each case, draw conclusions across instances, and create a cross-case report [8]. Researchers may have generalizable discoveries and construct ideas using data from numerous cases [9].

There are four cases compared, such as Schoters, Triple Jeans, Maicih, and Carl & Claire with Growth Hacking Framework and Value Co-Creation Framework.

ANALYSIS

The comparative case studies using the growth hacking framework by Bohnsack and Liesner [3] are elaborated on in the table below:

Figure IV. Comparative Studies with Growth Hacking Framework

Case Study	Digital Marketing Techniques	Data Analysis and Testing	Coding and Automation	Implications
Schoters	Activated digital marketing techniques (assisting the advertising setting, and giving recommendations for	Only data analysis, without testing (analyzing the industry)	Activated coding and automation (optimizing the	Optimized Digital Marketing Activations. Also, Schoters' growth hack manual is tested and more reliable in terms of digital marketing techniques and coding, and

	creative advertising content and funnel mapping)		website and landing page)	automation. However it is not tested in terms of data analysis, therefore it is less reliable as a manual
Triple Jeans	Activated digital marketing techniques (providing suggestions for their field resources on offline stores, and implementing KOL activation)	Only data analysis , without testing (analyzing the industry)	Activated coding and automation (optimizing digital advertising and digital marketing channels)	These actions resulted in better performance on social media metrics and a 33% increase in their followers' growth.
Maicih	Activated digital marketing techniques (providing recommendations for advertising content, and determining suitable funnel mapping)	Only data analysis , without testing (analyzing the industry)	Activated coding and automation ((optimizing the website (especially for UI/UX improvement), giving several suggestions for landing pages.))	Improved customer loyalty program.
Carl & Claire	Activated digital marketing techniques ((improve its Benefit Feature Guarantee (BFG) and unique selling proposition (USP). BDD's action is simply to develop and define content based on the marketing objective.))	Without data analysis and testing	Without Coding and Automation	This action resulted in a 0,25% increase in their CTR (Click Through Rate) and a 67% increase in their ROAs (Return on Ad Spent) during the advertising campaign during this period.

Figure V. Comparative Studies with Value Co-Creation Framework

Case Study	Co-production of value propositions (value in exchange)	Co-creation of value experiences (value in use)	Implications
Schoters	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No contracting for complementary resources, unclear assignments in advance for clients' representatives - There is an organization of resource integration (weekly meeting for discussions) - BDD growth hack team managed to generate positive results (cultivation of the output of co-production) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Co-creation of the conceptions of value based on both counterparts' discussions - BDD growth hack team do control the contingencies of use - Growth hack team assessment of the outcome by reports and evaluation 	Positive results heavily come from the growth hack team from BDD. Since there is no contracting for clients, clients tend to not work on their assignments.

Triple Jeans	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No contracting for complementary resources, unclear assignments in advance for clients' representatives - There is no organization of resource integration between the growth hack team and clients' representatives(weekly meeting only for reports and follow-ups) - BDD growth hack team managed to generate positive results (cultivation of the output of co-production) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Co-creation of the conceptions of value based on both counterparts' discussions - BDD growth hack team do controlling the contingencies of use - No controlling the contingencies statement since the growth hack team did not require to make a growth hack manual by the client 	Positive results heavily come from growth hack team from BDD. Since there is no contracting for clients, clients tend to not working on their assignments. Moreover BDD did not conduct discussions weekly with clients, and resource is not integrated and only limited to growth hack team resources.
Maicih	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No contracting for complementary resources, unclear assignments in advance for clients' representatives - There is an organization of resource integration (weekly meeting for discussions) - BDD growth hack team managed to generate positive results (cultivation of the output of co-production) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Co-creation of the conceptions of value based on both counterparts' discussions - BDD growth hack team does control the contingencies of use - Growth hack team assessment of the outcome by reports and evaluation 	Positive results heavily come from the growth hack team from BDD. Since there is no contracting for clients, clients tend to not work on their assignments
Carl & Claire	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No contracting for complementary resources, unclear assignments in advance for clients' representatives - There is no organization of resource integration between the growth hack team and clients' representatives(weekly meeting only for reports and follow-ups) - BDD growth hack team managed to generate positive results (cultivation of the output of co-production) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Co-creation of the conceptions of value based on both counterparts' discussions - BDD growth hack team does control the contingencies of use - Growth hack team assessment of the outcome by reports and evaluation 	Positive results heavily come from the growth hack team from BDD. Since there is no contracting for clients, clients tend to not work on their assignments. Moreover, BDD did not conduct discussions weekly with clients, the resource is not integrated and only limited to growth hack team resources.

Based on the comparison analysis with the growth hacking framework, the absence of testing practices for data analysis affects mostly the cases with growth hack manual requests. BDD's performance is sufficient to clients' expectations even with current practices, but with the new framework generated from this analysis, BDD could increase its competitive advantage.

FINDINGS

According to the growth hacking framework by Bohnsack and Liesner [3], BDD practices a strategy breakdown list that is fitting. However, BDD doesn't divide the list into a growth hacking framework in which it should, therefore BDD could assign works in a

more seamless manner. In addition, in the data analysis and testing part, BDD could add some testing practices to the strategy breakdown list, for example, using A/B testing.

To supplement BDD’s growth hack as a service, value co-creation theory is also added to the revised framework to provide a better process of growth hacking with clients. At its most basic level, A/B testing is a method for contrasting two versions of anything to determine which works better [10].

As for the growth hack service framework for BDD, it is using the combination of the growth hacking framework by Bohnsack and Liesner [3] and value creation by Kohtamäki & Rajala [4] as mapped below:

Figure VI. Comparative Studies with Growth Hacking Framework

The author added up a value creation agreement to establish appropriate collaboration in B2B systems for value creation. The author also added up A/B testing activations before any digital marketing techniques or coding and automation activities, this complements the making of a growth hacking manual for clients containing each component. Based on the author’s interview with BDD’s representative, they have weekly meetings with growth hack service clients to discuss about each strategy breakdown in the list. Before each meeting, the author suggests BDD’s growth hack team remind clients about the value creation and discuss value in exchange and value in use assignments for both BDD and its clients and follow up on each progress regularly. Most importantly, based on the comparison analysis with the value creation framework, BDD needs to contract for complementary resources and consistently conduct an assessment of the outcome to deliver an appropriate collaboration in B2B systems for value creation.

CONCLUSION & RECOMMENDATION

BDD growth hack service practice is close to Bohnsack and Liesner [3] and Kohtamäki & Rajala [4] growth hack framework, but lacking in data analysis and testing. The author suggested a new framework that combines the growth hack framework and the value creation framework. New operational instructions include value creation agreements and A/B testing based on comparative analysis. BDD should also remind clients about value creation and discuss value in exchange and value in use assignments. The new framework should increase service quality and resource availability of BDD growth hack service.

The operational instructions should be tested in real practices and revised accordingly if needed. The composition of digital marketing techniques, data analysis, and testing, as well as coding and automation, should also be revised accordingly. The amount of value-creation practice assignments for each counterpart should also be adjusted accordingly to BDD’s clients’ nature. Future research of the output generated from the new growth hack service framework is appropriate for more insights into BDD growth hack service.

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